

Influence of Leadership Styles on Job Performance of Academic Librarians in Federal University Libraries in North-West, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19485079>

Abstract

The study examined the impact of leadership styles on the job performance of academic librarians in Federal University Libraries across North-West Nigeria, with a specific focus on transformational and transactional leadership. A descriptive survey design was employed for the research. The population comprised 179 academic librarians from seven federal universities in North-West Nigeria: Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria; Bayero University, Kano; Federal University Dutse, Jigawa; Federal University Gusau, Zamfara; Federal University Dutsinma, Katsina; Federal University Kebbi; and Usman Danfodio University. Total population sampling was used, and data were collected via a structured questionnaire. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, such as the mean and standard deviation, conducted in SPSS. Results indicated that transformational leadership significantly affects the job performance of academic librarians, with librarians viewing their leaders as role models who inspire, encourage creativity, and support professional development. Similarly, transactional leadership was found to positively impact job performance through clear task allocation, performance monitoring, rewards, accountability, and prompt feedback. The study concludes that effective leadership practices substantially enhance the productivity, motivation, and service quality of academic librarians in federal university libraries. It recommends ongoing leadership training for library managers and the development of a supportive work environment to improve librarians' job performance.

Keywords: Leadership styles, Job performance, Academic librarians

Introduction

The job performance of academic librarians is a vital factor in determining the effectiveness and efficiency of university libraries in achieving their aims. Academic librarians are responsible for curating, managing, and disseminating knowledge resources that support teaching, learning, and research within the university system (Okiki, 2020). Their performance is reflected in their ability to meet the evolving needs of students, faculty, and researchers, adapt to technological advancements, and offer innovative services. High job performance among academic librarians improves the quality of library services, encourages academic excellence, and helps achieve the institution's overall goals (Adeniran & Onuoha, 2018). Conversely, low performance may restrict access to and usability of library resources, negatively impacting the academic community. Performance among academic librarians is affected by both individual and organisational factors. Personal attributes such as motivation, competence, and job satisfaction are crucial. Organisational factors, including leadership style, resource availability, and workplace environment, also influence job

performance (Usman & Abdulkadir, 2019). The interaction of these elements emphasises the need to examine how leadership style and job satisfaction influence the performance of academic librarians.

Leadership style is a vital factor shaping job performance in any organisation. It defines how leaders influence their subordinates, make decisions, and interact with their teams. In academic libraries, the leadership style adopted by library directors or heads significantly affects librarians' motivation, engagement, and overall performance (Aslam & Safdar, 2020). The importance of leadership style in academic settings cannot be overstated. Leaders in academic libraries are tasked with guiding their teams to achieve the institution's broader objectives, which include effective knowledge management, service delivery, and the integration of technological advancements. Transformational leadership, for instance, has been found to inspire and motivate employees by creating a vision, fostering innovation, and addressing employees' intrinsic needs. In the library context, transformational leaders empower librarians to adopt new technologies and improve service delivery (Yusuf & Alabi, 2022). Transformational leaders not only focus on achieving immediate goals but also invest in their staff's professional development, thereby enhancing job performance. In this study, the research considers transformational, transactional, and participative leadership styles as the variables.

Transformational leadership is vital in academic libraries as it inspires and motivates librarians by creating a compelling vision, fostering innovation, and addressing intrinsic needs. This leadership style empowers librarians to adopt new technologies, improve service delivery, and constantly enhance their performance. Transformational leaders go beyond merely managing tasks; they provide direction, motivation, and opportunities for professional development, which are essential in today's rapidly changing academic landscape. In academic libraries, transformational leadership involves not just managing resources but developing a shared vision that aligns with the institution's broader goals, such as advancing research, supporting student learning, and integrating technological innovations (Bass, 1999; Northouse, 2019; Tims et al., 2011). A key aspect of transformational leadership is establishing a shared vision that motivates librarians to work toward common objectives. Leaders articulate a future vision for the library, helping librarians understand how their roles contribute to wider institutional goals. This method boosts job satisfaction, engagement, and alignment with the library's aims. Clear communication of this vision fosters a sense of purpose among librarians, encouraging them to perform at their best (Yusuf & Alabi, 2022). In regions like North-West Nigeria, where universities encounter significant challenges such as limited resources and funding, transformational leaders are especially crucial. These leaders motivate their teams to excel despite constraints, fostering a culture of innovation and resourcefulness. They encourage librarians to look beyond limitations and seek alternative solutions, such as developing partnerships with other institutions or championing open-access resources. By promoting creativity and adaptability, these leaders ensure that libraries continue to flourish even under difficult circumstances (Ahmed & Suleiman, 2019).

Another vital aspect of transformational leadership in academic libraries is its emphasis on fostering adaptability, especially in the face of technological advancements. Transformational leaders offer ongoing professional development opportunities, encouraging librarians to stay current with new technologies and trends in library science. This not only enhances service delivery but also helps ensure that the library remains relevant in a digital age. By investing in the professional growth of librarians, transformational leaders build a workforce prepared to meet new challenges, thereby driving the library's success and innovation (Bass, 1999; Tims et al., 2011). Additionally, transformational leaders recognise that job

satisfaction is deeply connected to intrinsic factors such as career development and autonomy. In academic libraries, these leaders support the professional growth of librarians through training, encouraging participation in conferences, and promoting further education. This focus on personal development helps librarians feel valued and supported, which in turn boosts their job satisfaction and performance. Transformational leaders also acknowledge individual and team achievements, which improves morale and cultivates a culture of excellence. When librarians feel appreciated, they are more likely to exceed expectations in their roles, leading to improved service delivery and job performance (Bass & Riggio, 2006; Northouse, 2018; Tims et al., 2011).

Transactional Leadership concentrates on structured tasks, rewards, and penalties based on performance. This approach guarantees compliance and the achievement of short-term goals, such as meeting deadlines and following policies. While transactional leadership might not encourage creativity, it is essential for maintaining structure and accountability in library operations. In the Nigerian context, where bureaucratic systems often prevail, transactional leadership ensures that librarians comply with institutional policies and accomplish set objectives. Nonetheless, its excessive focus on control can restrict innovation and reduce job satisfaction (Aslam & Safdar, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

Leadership is vital in shaping how organisations function and how employees perform. In academic libraries, where delivering quality services depends largely on librarians' skills and motivation, the leadership style of library management can significantly affect job performance. Despite the essential role of academic librarians in supporting teaching, learning, and research at universities, there have been ongoing issues, including low productivity, low motivation, and poor job satisfaction, among library staff in some federal universities in North-West Nigeria.

Research indicates that various leadership styles, such as transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire, can have different effects on employee performance. However, there is limited empirical evidence on how these leadership styles specifically influence the job performance of academic librarians within the context of federal university libraries in North-West Nigeria. This gap raises concerns about whether current leadership practices are effectively improving librarians' productivity, commitment, and overall contribution to their institutions' academic mission.

Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the influence of leadership style and job satisfaction on job performance of academic librarians in Federal University Libraries in North-West, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Examine the influence of transformational leadership style on the job performance of academic librarians in Federal University Libraries in North-West, Nigeria.
2. Assess the influence of transactional leadership style on the job performance of academic librarians in Federal University Libraries in North-West, Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design for this study is descriptive. The population of the study consists of one hundred and seventy-nine (179) Academic Librarians, drawn from seven (7) Federal universities in North-West Nigeria: Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria 96; Bayero University, Kano 40; Federal University Dutse, Jigawa 7; Federal University Gusau, Zamfara 12; Federal University Dutsinma, Katsina 10; Federal University Kebbi 7; and Usman Danfodio University 7. This study adopted the total population as the sampling frame, which is a specialised form of purposive sampling. A questionnaire was used as the data collection instrument. The data collected in this study will be analysed using both descriptive statistical techniques. SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) will be used for data analysis.

Results and Discussion

The results of the data analysis are presented according to the research questions formulated for the study. Data related to each research question are presented on a separate table to aid comprehension of the analysis and interpretation of results.

Research Question One: To what extent does transformational leadership style influence the job performance of academic librarians in Federal University Libraries in North-West, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on Transformational Leadership and Job Performance of Academic Librarians

Item No	Item Description	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
1	My leader acts as a role model by demonstrating high ethical standards in the library.	172	2.88	0.95	High Extent
2	My leader motivates me by defining clear objectives for the library's future.	172	3.05	0.98	High Extent
3	My leader encourages me to think creatively about innovative solutions to library challenges.	172	2.91	0.97	High Extent
4	My leader provides me with individualised attention to my professional development needs.	172	2.98	1.03	High Extent
5	My leader communicates high expectations that inspire me to improve my work performance.	172	2.84	0.98	High Extent
6	My leader fosters an environment where I feel comfortable sharing new ideas without fear of criticism.	172	3.04	0.97	High Extent
7	My leader recognises my individual contributions to the library's goals.	172	2.83	1.03	High Extent
8	My leader demonstrates confidence in my abilities to perform tasks effectively.	172	2.94	0.93	High Extent
9	My leader encourages teamwork and cooperation among academic librarians to enhance job performance.	172	3.03	0.98	High Extent

10	My leader allows me to ask about new job problems.	172	2.98	0.97	High Extent
Grand Mean			2.97	0.98	

Table 1 shows a grand mean of 2.97, indicating that respondents generally agreed to a high degree that transformational leadership style positively influences the job performance of academic librarians. This suggests that librarians see their leaders as role models who inspire, motivate, and support them professionally, fostering creativity, accountability, and teamwork in library operations. The overall standard deviation of 0.98 reflects moderate variation in responses, showing that while many librarians strongly agree with the presence of transformational leadership practices, some respondents rated these practices slightly lower. This indicates that transformational leadership positively contributes to librarians' job performance, supporting effective service delivery in academic libraries.

Research Question Two: To what extent does transactional leadership style influence the job performance of academic librarians in Federal University Libraries in North-West, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Transactional Leadership and Job Performance of Academic Librarians

Item No	Item Description	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
11	My leader provides clear rewards or incentives when I meet/exceed job expectations.	172	2.90	1.01	High Extent
12	My leader regularly monitors my work to ensure I meet established job standards.	172	2.98	0.96	High Extent
13	My leader encourages me to work efficiently to meet job deadlines.	172	3.00	0.95	High Extent
14	My leader clearly outlines specific tasks/responsibilities I need to accomplish.	172	2.91	0.96	High Extent
15	My leader motivates me to perform better by offering rewards such as bonuses/recognition.	172	2.84	1.03	High Extent
16	My leader uses corrective actions to improve my work performance when necessary.	172	3.02	0.95	High Extent
17	My leader's leadership positively influences my productivity.	172	2.85	0.97	High Extent
18	My leader makes me realise the consequences of poor job performance.	172	2.87	1.05	High Extent
19	My leader holds me accountable for my duties at work.	172	2.92	0.92	High Extent
20	I receive timely feedback from my leader when my performance falls short of expectations.	172	3.06	0.96	High Extent
Grand Mean			2.90	0.98	

Table 2 presents a grand mean of 2.90, indicating that respondents generally agree that the transactional leadership style positively affects the job performance of academic librarians. This suggests that leaders

who offer clear rewards, monitor performance, enforce accountability, and provide timely feedback are seen as improving librarians' productivity and efficiency. The overall standard deviation of 0.98 indicates moderate variation in responses, meaning that while most librarians recognise the positive impact of transactional leadership, a few respondents rated it slightly lower.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed a strong positive relationship between transformational leadership and academic librarians' job performance. The results indicate that librarians who view their leaders as role models—motivating, supportive, and attentive to their professional development—achieve higher performance levels. This suggests that transformational leadership practices promote greater commitment, innovation, and efficiency among academic librarians. The findings also reinforce earlier research, such as Ugwu and Okore (2020), who observed that transformational leadership significantly predicted improved knowledge-sharing behaviour and job performance among librarians. Likewise, Akanmidu et al. (2021) reported that transformational leadership had a more substantial positive impact on service delivery than transactional leadership. While these studies affirm the significance of transformational leadership in library environments, this research adds to the discussion by providing empirical evidence on its specific influence on the job performance of academic librarians in the selected institutions. Overall, the results bolster the argument that leadership practices—including mentoring, ethical modelling, fostering creativity, and supporting professional growth—are essential for enhancing librarians' productivity and the overall quality of library services.

The findings of this study show that transactional leadership significantly enhances librarians' job performance. Librarians who receive clear task assignments, systematic performance monitoring, and structured reward and accountability systems tend to execute their duties more effectively. These practices clarify expectations and support adherence to institutional goals, thereby improving efficiency and service delivery in library operations. Although this result aligns with the findings of Quadri et al. (2023), who observed that transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership styles collectively influence job performance, the present study offers further insight by emphasising the specific role of transactional leadership within the context of library work. Library tasks are often procedural, deadline-driven, and service-oriented; hence, leadership approaches that prioritise clear performance standards, regular feedback, and reward systems may be particularly effective in motivating librarians to uphold high-quality work and meet institutional expectations. This suggests that transactional leadership can contribute both practically and strategically to enhancing performance management in library organisations.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that leadership style significantly influences the job performance of academic librarians in Federal University Libraries in North-West Nigeria. The study found that transformational, transactional, and participative leadership styles positively affect librarians' effectiveness and efficiency at work, with effective leadership and job satisfaction factors contributing considerably to enhancing librarians' productivity, motivation, and quality of service delivery.

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made to enhance the job performance of academic librarians in Federal University Libraries in North-West Nigeria:

1. University and library management should organise regular training sessions and workshops for library leaders to enhance transformational, transactional, and participative leadership skills. This will ensure that librarians receive ethical guidance, motivation, clear objectives, and support for participative decision-making.
2. University management should provide a conducive physical workspace, access to necessary resources, reasonable workloads, and policies that promote collaboration and efficiency. A supportive environment boosts librarians' productivity and decreases work-related stress.

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